

Soil and Crop Management

Effect of planting method and fertilizer combination on deep water rice yield on the Cuu Long Delta

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We studied transplanted or broadcast-seeded Nang Tay Dum (floating rice) at 4 fertilizer levels—0 fertilizer, 40 kg N/ha, 40-18 kg NP/ha, or 40-18-33 kg NPK/ha—in 1983 wet season at Thot Not. The trial was in 3 replications in a split-plot design with planting method in main plots and fertilizer combinations in 18-m² subplots. Soil was a Sulfaquept with pH 4.5, 0.178% N, 0.067% P₂O₅, 0.067% SO₄, 2.88 meq Al³⁺/100 g, and 0.56 meq H⁺/100 g. Plots reached 120-cm water depth in mid-Oct.

Yields of Nang Tay Dum under different planting methods and fertilizer combinations,^a Hau Giang, Vietnam, 1983.

Planting method	Yield (t/ha)				
	F0	F1	F2	F3	Mean
Broadcast	1.6	1.3	1.9	2.0	1.73
Transplanted	0.7	0.3	1.8	1.7	1.11
LSD 5%					
Planting method					ns
Fertilizer combinations					0.28
Fertilizer combinations at same planting method					0.40
Planting methods at same fertilizer combinations					1.16

^aF0 = no fertilizer, F1 = 40 kg N/ha, F2 = 40-18 kg NP/ha, F3 = 40-18-33 kg NPK/ha.

Seeds were broadcast at 100 kg/ha or 35-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing. N was applied 30 d after broadcasting or 10 d after transplanting. PK was applied basally.

The effect of fertilizer combinations and interaction between fertilization and planting method were significant (see

table). Fertilizers did not significantly increase yield of broadcast-seeded rice. For transplanted rice, NP gave best results and N alone did not increase yield over that of the control. Acid sulfate conditions may have decreased response to fertilizer N. □

Effect of planting method and fertility levels on floating rice grown on acid-sulfate soils on the Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam

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Floating rice on the Cuu Long (Mekong) Delta is broadcast seeded on dry soil in May and Jun and the crop is not fertilized. Soil pH is from 3.7 to 5.0 early in the cropping season and increases steadily as

floodwater accumulates. We studied the effect of stand establishment and fertilizer application on floating rice yield in a farmer field in Thot Not District of Hau Giang Province.

The trial was in a split-plot design with planting treatments in main plots and fertilizer combinations in subplots (Table 1,2). Soil was clay acid-sulfate with 0.178% total N, 0.029% total P, 0.067% SO₄²⁻, and 2.889 meq Al³⁺ and 0.586 meq H⁺/100 g soil. Seeds of floating rice Nang Tay Dum were broadcast on dry soil at 100 kg/ha on 7 Jun 1983. Seeds fix

transplanting were sown in the nursery on the same day. Forty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 25- × 25-cm spacing when enough rain for puddling the soil had fallen. P and K were applied at transplanting as superphosphate and muriate of potash. N was applied 15 d after sowing the broadcast crop and at puddling in the transplanted crop. Maximum field water depth reached 100 cm in early Nov, which

Table 2. Grain yield of floating rice as influenced by planting method and fertilizer application in an acid-sulfate soil of the Cuu Long Delta, Vietnam.

Planting method	Grain yield (t/ha) ^a				
	F ₀	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	
Broadcast	1.6	1.3	1.9	2.0	
Transplanting	0.7	0.3	1.8	1.7	
CD at 5%					
Method of stand establishment					ns
Fertility level					0.28
Fertility level at a constant level					0.41
Method of stand establishment at a constant level of fertility or at different levels of fertility					1.16

^aF₀ = no fertilizer, F₁ = 40 kg N/ha, F₂ = 40-17.5 kg NP/ha, F₃ = 40-17.5-22.5 kg NPK/ha,

Table 1. Plant characters of floating rice as influenced by planting method and fertilizer interaction in an acid-sulfate soil in Hau Giang, Vietnam.^a

Plant character	Broadcast					Transplanted				
	F ₀	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean	F ₀	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	Mean
Height (cm)	105	184	189	189	187	170	170	175	175	173
Maturity (d)	175	175	170	170	173	180	180	170	170	175
Panicles/m ²	93	87	82	95	89	49	42	70	74	59
Panicle length (cm)	18	19	19	20	19	18	18	20	21	19
Panicle weight (g)	2.7	2.5	3.4	3.9	3.1	2.9	2.4	4.4	4.4	3.5
Filled grains/panicle	108	117	124	191	135	103	79	145	180	127
Unfilled grains (%)	28	36	24	21	27	51	48	35	18	38
1,000-grain weight (g)	22.4	22.3	21.7	22.7	22.3	21.0	21.5	22.4	22.4	21.8

^aF₀ = no fertilizer, F₁ = 40 kg N/ha, F₂ = 40-17.5 kg NP/ha, F₃ = 40-17.5-22.5 kg NPK/ha.

is about 50 cm lower than normal.

The interaction between planting method and fertilizer application significantly influenced grain yield (Table 2). Adding NP or NPK increased yield of broadcast seeded rice over the control and N alone.

For transplanted rice, adding NP or NPK significantly increased yields above

the control and N alone. Applying N alone decreased yield 64% below that of the control as there was a significant reduction in panicle number and filled grains/panicle.

Adding N alone appeared to aggravate Al toxicity, which reduced root growth. Adding P appeared to enhance root development and therefore nutrient absorption.

Adding K did not affect yield.

The adverse effect of N alone on grain yield was less pronounced in the broadcast crop because it had higher plant density than the transplanted crop. Results suggest that closer spacing and P application are essential to improve density of the transplanted crop and therefore grain yield. □

Factors affecting critical P level for rice

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We conducted greenhouse and laboratory studies on soils with different texture, Olsen's extractable P, and CaCO₃ content. Olsen's P was higher in submerged soils than in air-dried soil (Table 1). Rice grain yield was significantly correlated with

Table 2. Effect of submergence and soil type on critical Olsen's level. Ludhiana, India.

Soil texture and type	Air-dried soil	Critical Olsen's P ^a		
		Submergence period (d)		
		1	3	7
Coarse (sand-sandy loam)	7.4 (0.89**)	12.5 (0.85**)	19.2 (0.75**)	19.9 (0.61**)
Medium (loam)	8.0 (0.99**)	11.1 (0.91**)	10.6 (0.88**)	10.5 (0.69**)
Fine (silty loam-silty clay loam)	8.4 (0.99**)	10.6 (0.82**)	13.4 (0.86**)	15.1 (0.91**)
High CaCO ₃ (loamy-sand-clay)	7.8 (0.71**)	19.0 (0.60**)	20.9 (0.54**)	22.7 (0.52**)

^a Figures in parentheses indicate the R² value. ** = significant at 1% level.

Table 1. Effect of submergence on Olsen's extractable P, Ludhiana, India.

Soil texture type	Air dried	Extractable P (ppm) ^a after submergence for			
		1 d	3 d	7 d	15 d
Coarse (sand-sandy loam)	0.5-8.5	1.5-19.5	2.5-22.5	5-20.5	5-20
Medium (loam)	1-10.5	2.5-13.5	3.5-14	4.2-13.5	4.5-16.5
Fine (silty loam-silty clay loam)	4-10.5	5-13.5	7.5-16	11-19	13-22
High CaCO ₃ (loamy sand-clay)	4.2-8.5 (5.6)	8.5-21.5 (13.8)	10-24 (15.2)	11.5-25.5 (16.6)	12.5-27.5 (18.8)

^a Figures in parentheses indicate the mean value.

Olsen's extractable P. Critical Olsen's P level for rice was calculated by quadratic regression equations. Critical P depended upon soil texture, CaCO₃ content, and period of submergence (Table 2). □

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Causes for different response to and availability of P in rice and wheat ecosystems

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We studied rice and wheat response to applied P in the greenhouse on soil with different texture, Olsen's P, and CaCO₃. We also noted the effect of temperature and moisture on Olsen's P.

Bray's percent yield was higher for rice than for wheat (Table 1). CaCO₃ soil content did not affect Bray's percent

Table 1. Effect of soil type on Bray's yield of rice and wheat, Ludhiana, India.

Soil	Soils (no.)	pH ^a	Olsen's P ^a (ppm)	Bray's yield ^b (%)	
				Rice	Wheat
Coarse	5	7.5-8.9 (8.2)	0.5-8.5 (4.1)	85.3	60.0
Medium	5	8-9.1 (8.4)	1-10.5 (4.5)	85.0	64.6
Fine	4	7-8.3 (7.9)	4-10.5 (6.6)	94.6	75.7
High CaCO ₃ (>8%)					
Fine	2	8-8.1 (8.1)	4.3-8.5 (6.4)	95.2	58.7
Coarse	2	8-8.2 (8.1)	4.5-5.5 (5)	84.4	64.7

^a Numbers in parentheses are the mean.

^b Bray's percent yield = $\frac{\text{yield without P}}{\text{yield with 30 ppm P}} \times 100$.